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IMPROVING UROLOGY REFERRALS FOR PROSTATE EXAMINATIONS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

According to research and local data, there is a need to improve urology referrals for prostate examinations. Identified barriers to proper urology referrals include contradictory guidelines, confusing decision-making aids, and providers' knowledge deficit. A Delphi panel consisting of four multidisciplinary physicians from internal medicine, radiation oncology, surgical pathology, and urology in the Los Angeles area were recruited to obtain consensus feedback. The Delphi panel ranked existing Prostate-Specific Antigen (PSA) screening guidelines in this order: American Urological Association's guideline first, American Cancer Society second, and American Society of Clinical Oncology third. They agreed on the importance of PSA value interpretation staying consistent with current urological practices today and emphasized the importance of identifying risk factors for prostate cancer. Although only one of four physicians on the panel used a tool for calculating life expectancy, all agreed on PSA screening in the 50-59 age group, and two of four also included age groups 40-49, 60-69, and 70-79. Future implications include pilot testing this updated PSA testing tool, which incorporates user-centered design with local primary care providers (PCPs) as a reliable decision-making aid to help improve urology referrals for prostate examinations thereby saving cost, time, and lives.

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BACKGROUND

According to the American Cancer Society (ACS) (2018a), one in nine men will have prostate cancer during their lifetime in the United States. Prostate cancer is responsible for the deaths of one in 41 men, and it is the second leading cancer-related death among American men. Prostate cancer primarily develops in older and African-American men. Six out of 10 prostate cancer diagnoses are for men 65 years and above with the average age of diagnosis at 66 years. The 2018 estimation of new prostate cancer diagnosis in the United States is 164,690 with the highest incidence in California at 15,190 (ACS, 2018a). Consequently, in 2015, the latest cost of cancer care in the United States was estimated at \$80.2 billion (ACS, 2018b).

Despite the prevalence of prostate cancer both nationally and locally, the ratio of urologists per 100,000 population in California is 3.31, compared to the highest ratio in New Hampshire of 5.24 (American Urological Association [AUA], 2016a). This disparity illuminates the need for efficient use of urology referrals. Specifically, the AUA estimates the shortage of urologists in California with workforce statistics that found 1,298 active urologists, which is equivalent to 30,239 people per urologist. Additionally, the rapidly aging population in the United States is also fueling the demand for their services (Population Reference Bureau, 2014).

A frequent reason for seeking the attention of a urologist is for prostate cancer risk assessment that includes Prostate-Specific Antigen (PSA) screening and Digital Rectal Exam (DRE) (UCLA Health, n.d.). Despite frequent use and dependence of PSA testing as part of prostate examination and shared decision-making, the recommendations from leading healthcare organizations are contradictory. For example, in 2012, the U.S.

Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) advised against routine PSA screening at any age, which was subsequently updated in 2018 to enable screening for men 55 to 69 years with shared-decision making (Pucheril et al., 2015; USPSTF, 2018). However, the AUA fully supports PSA screening for men between 55 to 69 (AUA, 2015). This is in conflict with ACS that recommends PSA screening for men older than 50 with moderate risk and men older than 40 with high risk (Pucheril et al., 2015). These contradictions are in part causing the primary care providers (PCPs) to inconsistently refer patients to urologists for prostate examinations, which may delay care. Research demonstrates that the delay in care between the first abnormal PSA and referral may be greater than 20 months, which is detrimental to patients who arrive at the urologists' office without consistent laboratory work (Stapleton, Johns, Kopsaftis, Tamblyn, & Pinnock, 2008).

Problem Statement

Inappropriate urology referrals are a consequence of the conflicting recommendations related to PSA testing. The ramification of this conflict was reflective in a Los Angeles urology practice clinic (Clinic). The Clinic has four providers, three urologists and one nurse practitioner who manage approximately 250 patients per week. This practice serves a mostly geriatric Armenian and Hispanic population. A significant portion of the patients referred to the Clinic are from the local primary care providers. For five years, the urology providers observed a high level of inappropriate referrals for prostate examinations. From 2016 to 2017, 40% of the referrals were not necessary as the majority presented with normal prostate examinations and 6% presented with advanced prostate cancer. Although there are several tools (decision-making aids) to guide the practice of primary care providers in screening for prostate cancer, it was unknown

whether the problem lay in the existing tools, the providers, or both in making the referrals.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to modify and update an evidence-based tool on PSA testing for primary care providers to improve appropriate urology referrals for prostate examinations. The specific aim is to develop an updated clinical tool on PSA testing for primary care providers based on current guidelines and urological practices using the modified Delphi method.

Supporting Framework

Conceptual and theoretical frameworks provide boundaries, structure, and direction to projects (Bonnell & Smith, 2014). They also define terms and concepts. A framework is crucial when developing a process change to maintain an overall consistency between the purpose, methods, and outcomes (Bonnell & Smith, 2014). A logic model and user-centered design theory provided the appropriate foundation to guide the development and evaluation of an updated evidence-based clinical tool on PSA testing (Wholey, 1979; Zachary, 2005). Additionally, to encourage use of consistent standards, a logic model and user-centered design that incorporated a modified Delphi method were used to provide expertise feedback for consensus definition (Sudore et al., 2017).

Logic Model

Joseph Wholey (1979) introduced a logic model to improve efficiency, effectiveness, and responsiveness of government programs. The logic model is a visual roadmap that allows smooth transition between the main processes and outcomes to

monitor goals and revisions (Figure 1) (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2017; McCawley, 2001). The collective inputs provide the foundation for the resulting outcomes, where the proper inputs initiate the logical flow of the correspondingly valuable activities, outputs, outcomes, and goals. This flexibility popularized and expanded the logic model across the various leading industries, such as in education, health, and technology.

For this project, the logic model synergistically supports the settings, goals, and outcomes (Bonnell & Smith, 2014). The logic model's processes build on relevance, quality, and impact for effective form of communication to gain support from the stakeholders (McCawley, 2001). The major categories of the logic model include: 1) inputs, 2) activities, 3) outputs, 4) short-term outcome, 5) intermediate outcome, and 6) long-term goals. Assessment and planning start under input and activities categories (CDC, 2017). The results of assessment and planning fall under outputs category (CDC, 2017). The outcomes and long-term goals are measurable consequences of input, activities, and outputs (CDC, 2017).

Inputs include all the resources for initial assessment that may include workforce, finances, equipment, knowledge, and collaborators to demonstrate to the stakeholders that the project is of high quality (McCawley, 2001). This project's inputs include abstracting preliminary data from the Clinic to assess referral patterns, literature review, and existing clinical tools.

Activities are results of inputs for planning program events or strategies that affect outputs (CDC, 2017). The Clinic's EMR data abstraction activity found that a significant number of the primary care providers' referrals were not necessary due to normal prostate

examinations and many were overdue with advanced prostate cancer. The literature review provided ample evidence of primary care providers' inconsistent referral patterns because of the conflicting current guidelines and urological practices. As a result, the current clinical tools on PSA screening derived from this conflict are difficult to interpret. A Delphi panel from internal medicine, radiation oncology, surgical pathology, and urology were recruited from the Los Angeles area to guide standardization of the current clinical guidelines and urological practices through consensus definition.

Outputs are products of activities (CDC, 2017). The outputs provide the link between the problem and the intended outcome through publications, decision aids, teaching events, and application activities (McCawley, 2001). Synthesis of evidence-based guidelines, urological practices, and tools provides the link between the intended outcomes and the problem.

Outcomes describe expected effects in relation to time (CDC, 2017). The short-term outcome involves selecting an evidence-based tool for urological practices to update. According to the researchers, "In an area that lacks certainty, the Delphi method uses multiple rounds of structured feedback to achieve consensus" (Sudore et al., 2017). The intermediate outcome includes revising and adapting the new clinical tool from the Delphi panel's feedback for optimal utilization. The long-term goal is to demonstrate the impact of the behavioral changes that lead to changes in condition (McCawley, 2001). The long-term outcome is to evaluate the modified tool and integrate the modified tool into practice by the local primary care providers to facilitate changes in their current behavioral pattern.

User-Centered Design

The project incorporates user-centered design procedures in the development of the evidence-based clinical tool. Although Donald Norman introduced user-centered design theory in response to frustration with technology, this theory was quickly applied to other environments. His theory aimed to maximize end-user experience through improved communication between the innovators and the individuals using the new technology (Zachary, 2005). To help improve communication, the user-centered design theory includes preliminary testing, user satisfaction assessment, product usability assessment, and impact analysis (Brunner et al., 2017).

The specific elements of the user-centered design theory are closely intertwined with the modified Delphi method. The traditional Delphi method consists of 5 to 60 anonymous panelists with ongoing detailed feedback to build consensus; however, this approach was modified to four panelists with limited quantitative questions due to time and financial constraints (Sudore et al., 2017). Furthermore, the clinical tool must incorporate the needs of the end users to implement change in their behaviors. In a time of information overload, one of the major needs of the end user is the simple access to information. Convenient access to relevant information encourages receptiveness to change and higher utility of the product. Therefore, under the guidance of the Delphi panel, the preliminary revisions of the clinical tool must incorporate user experience and usability. The final clinical tool will then proceed to the pilot study with a group of primary care providers for impact analysis in a future study. The user-centered design theory was crucial in this project where the primary care providers' experience in

accessing the evidence-based tool will help determine their practice behaviors and organizational patterns (Figure 1).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

The review of literature focuses on research articles on PSA screening practices that affect primary care providers' urology referrals for prostate examinations. Specifically, the review consists of five sections: 1) pathophysiology and definition of terms, 2) PSA screening practices, 3) decision making process, 4) current guidelines, and 5) practice patterns and attitudes of primary care providers. A brief pathophysiology and definition of terms provide context to the literature review. Using the logic model and user-centered design, the aim was to develop an updated clinical tool on PSA testing based on the relevant literature review, current guidelines, and evidence-based urological practices. The modified Delphi method provided structured feedback for consensus definition to guide tool modification.

This literature review consisted of using the databases PubMed, CINAHL, and Google Scholar. Search terms included biomarkers tumor analysis, health screening utilization, men's health, prostate cancer screening, PSA, PSA screening tools, and urology. Additional search terms included PSA screening behaviors, patterns, and attitudes of primary care providers. Search limitations included scholarly articles published from 2008-2018 and English language only. The 10-year search period was necessary to compare PSA screening practices before and after the 2012 USPSTF's recommendation against routine PSA screening. The articles of preference were systematic reviews when applicable. Exclusion criteria included articles that focused primarily on digital rectal examination and metastatic prostate cancer.

Pathophysiology and Definition of Terms

The prostate is a male sex accessory gland that surrounds the urethra. The prostate consists of four main anatomical sites known as anterior, peripheral, central, and the transition zones (AUA, 2016b). The majority of prostatic carcinomas develop in the peripheral zone, while benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) stems from the transition zone. The prostatic fluid (consisting of acid, zinc, and serine protease known as PSA) combines with sperm and seminal vesicle fluid to form semen. On post mortem examination, approximately 70% of men over 70 years old were found to have prostate cancer (AUA, 2016b).

The PSA screening and DRE along with other identified variables are the screening tools to help with early detection of prostate cancer. However, BPH, infection, instrumentation, and other causes of inflammation may also contribute to elevated PSA values, which may lead to overdiagnosis (AUA, 2016b). Prostate cancer treatment may result in bowel dysfunction, urinary dysfunction, and impotence; thus, the benefits and risks of PSA testing remain controversial (AUA, 2016b). The literature establishes a need for a consensus when interpreting PSA levels in the medical community and the importance of shared decision-making.

Definition of Terms

Age adjusted PSA. Estimated 70% of patients with an elevated PSA value between four and 10 will have a negative prostate biopsy result (AUA, 2016b). Therefore, the general age-adjusted PSA (ng/dL) are as follows: age 40 - 49 = 2.5, 50 - 59 = 3.5, 60 - 69 = 4.5, and 70 - 79 = 6.5 (AUA, 2016b).

Free-complexed PSA. Serum PSA exists as free and complexed to protease inhibitors (AUA, 2016b). Patients with prostate cancer generally have a higher percentage of PSA complexed to protease inhibitors, and the free form is used to better understand the need for prostate biopsy in PSA levels between four and 10 (AUA, 2016b). Free PSA values above 25% help predict unlikelihood of clinically significant prostate cancer (AUA, 2016b).

Gleason score. Standard measure of the differentiation prostate cancer consisting of five patterns using the biopsy material (1-5 with 5 being the worst), where the sum of the two numbers calculate the final Gleason score (e.g., 3 + 5 = 8) (AUA, 2016b).

Prostate cancer staging. Malignant Tumors (TNM) staging is a notation system, which is used for prostate cancer staging as follows: a) T1 refers to stage of disease found by non-palpable method, b) T1a and T1b refers to prostate cancer incidentally found in tissue c) T1c refers cancers found during biopsy with an elevated PSA d) T2 refers to palpable cancer, and e) T3 refers to disease palpable outside the prostate (AUA, 2016b).

PSA density. Calculation of PSA density by dividing the absolute PSA level by the prostate volume (mL) obtained by transrectal ultrasound or MRI (AUA, 2016b). A PSA density >0.15 qualifies for prostate biopsy (AUA, 2016b).

PSA velocity. Measure PSA trends of at least three measurements during a 2-year period (AUA, 2016b). The threshold is 0.35 ng/ml/year for PSA values <4 ng/ml and 0.75 ng/ml/year for PSA value >4 ng/ml (AUA, 2016b).

Sensitivity and specificity. The most common cutoff to flag for an abnormal PSA level is 4.0 ng/mL. The approximate sensitivity of the 4.0 ng/mL cutoff is 21 percent for detecting all types of prostate cancer and 51 percent for detecting high-grade cancers

(UpToDate, 2018). The 3.0 ng/mL cutoff increased these sensitivities to 32 percent for detecting all types of cancer and 68 percent for detecting high-grade cancer (UpToDate, 2018). However, the approximate specificity was 91 percent for 4.0 ng/mL and 85 percent for a 3.0 ng/mL cutoff (UpToDate, 2018).

Variable risks. The risks of prostate cancer are as follows: a) average risk refers to men over 50 year who are expected to live ≥ 10 more years, b) high risk refers to men over 45 who are African American, men who have a first-degree relative diagnosed with prostate cancer at age ≤ 65 , c) highest risk refers to men over 40 with more than one first-degree relatives diagnosed with prostate cancer at age ≤ 65 (ACS, 2016).

PSA Screening Practices

Cross, Ritter, & Reding (2011) investigated PSA screening patterns to determine the value of PSA levels and age-influenced treatment trends. Their study described a historical prospective of a population-based cohort of 385,000 patients in a single multi-specialty institution in rural Wisconsin. Their data recorded outcomes were from 1960 to 2011. From their analysis, the researchers were able to conclude that since the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approval of PSA and DRE screenings in 1994, younger men (from 70-71 to 67 years old) were diagnosed with prostate cancer. They found treatment patterns were decided based on the patient age, grade and stage of cancer, not the PSA values. Their data neither distinguish between aggressive and non-aggressive cancers and over-diagnosing prostate cancers as a result of PSA levels. A limitation of this study was their sample data were from patients already diagnosed with prostate cancer (Cross, Ritter, & Reding, 2011). The controversy on PSA screening manifests most clearly in two major randomized studies that are influencing current guidelines and practices.

The first study, the European Randomized Study of Screening for Prostate Cancer (ERSPC) correlated significant reductions in prostate cancer mortality after nine and 11 years of follow-up of screening in a group of European men 55-69 years, these results were confirmed after an expanded 13 years follow-up study (Schröder et al., 2014; Appendix I, Table I1). After 13 years, the absolute risk reduction of prostate cancer mortality was 1.28 per 1000 men randomized to PSA screening (95% CI 490 - 1929). Although the researchers acknowledged the positive results from screening, they also identified a need to evaluate the risk of harm before proceeding with generalized screening (Schröder et al., 2014). However, during the ERSPC study, sextet core biopsies were used rather than 12 core biopsies (50% less tissue samples) that are common today, which may have resulted in significant decrease in prostate cancer detection. Since the publication of this study, the risk of harm from prostate biopsies have been decreased substantially through the use of multiple tumor biomarker tests recently developed and available today (Punnen et al., 2017). For example, the 4kscore serum test was introduced in the mid-2010's to mitigate unnecessary prostate biopsies and their harms by reliably ($p < .01$) measuring risk for aggressive prostate cancer after the initial PSA testing. However, due to the high cost (approximately \$390 - \$1,900 per 4kscore test depending on insurance) and complex eligibility criteria, they are secondary tool to assess risk for prostate cancer (Punnen et al., 2017).

Another well designed randomized control study examined prostate cancer screening as part of the prostate, lung, colorectal, and ovarian cancer (PLCO) screening that took place with a group of American men 55-74 years (Andriole et al., 2012; Appendix I, Table I1). In contrast to the ERSPC study, these researchers found that 13

years after screening, there was no mortality benefit between the organized annual screening (intervention group [IG]) and the opportunistic screening group (control group [CG]). The relative risk of mortality was comparable in the IG versus the CG for men 55-64 years was 1.19 and 1.02 for men 65-74 years (Andriole et al., 2012).

In the PLCO study, 45% of the randomized group had at least one PSA test done three years before randomization and an estimated 52% of the CG obtained opportunistic PSA screening during the last round of testing for intervention arm (Andriole et al., 2012). The behaviors of participants with prior knowledge of their baseline PSA values may be different than those who are not aware of their baseline PSA values; thus, producing potential bias. Furthermore, the intervention group with PSA screening had $n = 2530$ compared to the control group at $n = 2265$ for Stage II (T1B or T1C) clinical stage diagnosis, while the Stage II (T2, T2A, T2B, or T2C) intervention group had $n = 1477$ and control group at $n = 1269$. These numbers suggest that the higher number of participants in the Stage II intervention groups where treatment would be most effective in averting approximately 25% risk of prostate cancer mortality is highly significant to encourage continued screening (Andriole et al., 2012; ARUP Consult, 2018; Banerji et al., 2016; Cooperberg, 2017). Similarly, in a systematic review on PSA population screening, the researchers noted that late detection of stages III-IV diagnosis and prostate cancer-related mortality demonstrated moderate levels of evidence in contrast to early Stage I detection of prostate cancer (Lee et al., 2013).

Decision Making Process

Clinical practice guidelines are an important bridge between evidence and practice (Rosenfeld, Shiffman, & Robertson, 2013). Despite the importance, only 54.9%

of patients in the United States received care according to guideline recommendations (Gagliardi, Brouwers, & Bhattacharyya, 2014). According to Gagliardi et al., implementation tools that reduce complexity of information help improve adherence to guideline recommendation. Additionally, although guidelines provide evidence-based recommendations, they do not replace professional clinical judgment (Rosenfeld et al., 2013).

The Institute of Medicine's (IOM) (2011) eight standards help establish trustworthiness to their guidelines. IOM's standards include: 1) transparency, 2) conflict of interest management, 3) multidisciplinary group composition, 4) clinical practice and systematic review synthesis, 5) rating strength of recommendations, 6) wording of recommendations, 7) third party review, and 8) updating. In this project, the logic model incorporates IOM's eight standards to help reconcile USPSTF's best practice guideline with the AUA's clinical guideline to adapt existing comprehensive tool on PSA testing (Figure 1). To establish transparency, written and electronic records were archived and available upon request. In addition, the Delphi panel convened from four multidisciplinary fields to mitigate conflict of interest. Furthermore, the three most influential guidelines were synthesized based on rigorous review of literature (AUA, 2016b; USPSTF 2018).

Both the National Institute of Health and the USPSTF refer to the IOM's standards for instituting rigorous clinical practice guidelines (IOM, 2011; Rosenfeld et al., 2013). The literature suggests a greater need for consistent implementation of complex guidelines through accompanying tools. The modified Delphi method provides user-centered standardization by integrating current guidelines and practices through

structured feedbacks (Gagliardi et al., 2014). The strength of their evaluation based on their ranking and feedback was the basis of the updated comprehensive tool, such as from The University of Texas MD Anderson Cancer Center and National Comprehensive Cancer Network (NCCN) (Appendix A; Appendix B).

A comprehensive tool is important to help guide providers when making a clinical decision (Rim et al., 2018). According to a study with 1,003 primary care physicians and 253 nurse practitioners regarding the use of decision aids for PSA screening, 54% of the participants did not use decision aids for PSA screening (only 11% did use decision aids), but they were interested in using them in their practice (Rim et al., 2018). An additional 46% of the participants expressed interest in an improved decision aid (Rim et al., 2018). Therefore, this study demonstrates the need for an updated user-centered tool based on current guidelines and clinical practices to improve user experience and compliance.

Lastly, after the conclusion of this project, the second phase will entail pilot testing the tool with third party PCPs, and updating the tool as needed before disseminating to the local PCP population. The long-term goal is for the local providers to integrate the modified tool into practice.

Current Guidelines

Although the ERSPC and PLCO results are conflicting, both studies influence current guidelines regarding prostate cancer screening (Table 1). In 2012, USPSTF (2012) recommended against routine PSA screening for prostate cancer with a grade D rating (based on A, B, C, D, I scale with grade A being the highest recommendation). However, in 2018, USPSTF updated their recommendation and upgraded their D rating to C for men 55 to 69 years with shared-decision making while maintaining grade D

rating for men 70 years or older (USPSTF, 2012b; USPSTF, 2018). It is important to note that the 2012 USPSTF's panel consisted of approximately 16 volunteer members who were all primary care providers without any urologists represented (USPSTF, 2012a). As a result of their previous recommendation against routine PSA screening, early-stage prostate cancer and rates of PSA screening declined from 36.9% in 2005 to 30.9% in 2013 (Jemal et al., 2015). Furthermore, in a post-2012 PSA screening recommendation impact study, researchers found that continued PSA screening for men <70 years of age could prevent more than one-half of avoidable prostate cancer related deaths while also reducing overdiagnoses (Gulati et al., 2014).

In 2018, USPSTF's final recommendation includes men 55 to 69 years of age in discussing the potential benefits and harms of PSA screening, which is more consistent with recommendations of the AUA (USPSTF, 2018). In 2015, the AUA stratified their guideline to include several new, more specific recommendations. For example, the AUA (2015) recommends *against* routine screening for men 40 to 54 years with average risk and men 70 plus years (or any men with less than 10 to 15-year life expectancy), but does recommend shared decision-making for men 55 to 69 years. The AUA recommendations are consistent with the majority of the radiation oncologists and urologists in a national survey (AUA, 2015; Kim et al., 2014). The AUA recommendations were developed by compiling published data, expert opinion, and clinical practice physicians (Forrest et al., 2009). The AUA guideline also includes age-adjusted PSA, density, velocity, and free/total ratio, which are consistent with standard practice among urological practices today (AUA, 2016b).

Similarly, the American Academy of Family Physicians (AAFP) (2018) recommends counseling men between 50 to 65 regarding the potential benefits and harms of PSA screening. Additionally, the American College of Physicians (ACP) (2010) recommends men in average-risk group to discuss potential benefits and harms of PSA screening at 50 years with at least a 10-year life expectancy and discussing screening earlier with men in a higher risk group. While the ACS (2016) recommends shared decision for men >50 years who are expected to live at least ten more years, >45 years for men at high risk, and >40 years for men at higher risk. Lastly, the American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO) recommends discussing with patients about the potential benefits and harms of PSA screening if their life expectancy is >10 years (Basch et al., 2012).

Although the 2018 USPSTF's final recommendation improves harmonization with the five leading organizations; however, these guidelines do not consistently distinguish between specific risk factors (e.g., African American group, first degree relatives with prostate cancer), which become problematic for the primary care providers to interpret (Carlsson et al., 2014; Cooperberg, 2017; Duke Institute of Health Innovation, 2018; The University of Texas MD Anderson Cancer Center, 2017). Therefore, despite the controversy related to PSA screening, the ability to mitigate any mortality through early detection and treatment of more advanced prostate cancer is a laudable goal.

Table 1

Current Guidelines

Organization	Age At Initial Screening	Life Expectancy	Intermediate Risk ^g	High Risk ^h	Highest Risk ⁱ
1. AAFP ^a	50-65				
2. ACS ^b		≥10 years	>50 years	>45years	>40 years
3. ACP ^c	50-69	≥10 years	>50 years	Earlier	Earlier
4. ASCO ^d		≥10 years			
5. AUA ^e	55-69	≥10-15 years		>40 years	
6. USPSTF ^f	55-69				

Note. ^a = American Academy of Family Physicians, ^b = American Cancer Society, ^c = American College of Physicians, ^d = American Society of Clinical Oncology, ^e = American Urological Association, ^f = U.S. Preventative Services Task Force, ^gIntermediate/average risk refers to men over 50 year who are expected to live ≥10 more years, ^hHigh risk refers to men over 45 who are African American, men who have a first-degree relative diagnosed with prostate cancer at age ≤65, ⁱHighest risk refers to men over 40 with more than one first-degree relatives diagnosed with prostate cancer at age ≤65 (ACS, 2016).

Practice Patterns and Attitudes of Primary Care Providers

Despite the best intent of these guidelines, many of the PCPs' urology referrals for prostate examinations are outside the national guidelines. In a study with 90.9% compliance with referral guidelines, the urology referrals that were made outside the national guidelines subsequently yielded 15.9% cancer diagnosis (Baughan, Keatings, & O'Neill, 2011). The urological referrals made outside the national guidelines suggest additional factors other than the guidelines influenced PCPs' referral decision (Baughan, Keatings, & O'Neill, 2011). PSA screening guidelines shape the attitudes and behaviors of the PCPs. Unfortunately, conflicting guidelines are contributing to the inconsistent PSA screening practices.

The current guidelines are contradictory about age, life expectancy, and risks as factors for prostate cancer screening. These contradictions are manifested in the PCPs'

inconsistent screening patterns (Appendix H, Table H2). In a study of PCPs' PSA screening perspectives shortly after the 2012 USPSTF's release of recommendation against routine PSA screening, providers reported discontinuing PSA screening at different ages. In this study, 66.4% of the providers reported difficulty predicting life expectancy (Pollack et al., 2012). The study explored what providers would accept and whether that would coincide with their own beliefs on life expectancy. The researchers found that the number of years in practice was a significant factor in deciding whether the PCPs recommended PSA screening (Donnelly, Sternberg, Ashikaga, Plante, & Perrapato, 2017; Hall et al., 2017). According to the researchers, 27.7% of physicians with less than 10 years in practice (96.1% citing 2012 USPSTF guidelines) recommend against PSA screening versus 55.9% of those with greater than 10 years of experience who recommend PSA screening (Donnelly et al., 2017; Hall et al., 2017). The common reasons for recommending PSA screening included patient's family history of prostate cancer, personal request, and African American ancestry (Hall et al., 2017).

The time over-lap between the overall decrease in PSA screening trend and significant increase in the PSA value at the time of urology referrals suggest optimal opportunity at the primary care level for early detection of prostate cancer was delayed (Cohn et al., 2014; Hutchinson et al., 2016). Part of the reason for the screening delays may be due to providers' identified knowledge deficit about prostate cancer risk in men over 50 years (Tasian et al., 2012). User-centered educational tools may help improve providers' knowledge deficit, screening practices, and referral behaviors. For example, in research that studied the relationship between educational printed material and prostate cancer screening, the researchers found that printed educational material changed the

patients' attitude significantly in favor of PSA cancer screening from 31% in the non-informed group to 93% in the informed group (Stamatiou et al., 2008).

The literature review highlights conflicting practice guidelines that may contribute to the ambivalence among PCPs to make screening decisions related to prostate cancer. Additionally, conflicting guidelines may delay in referrals for men with early stage prostate cancer. Clarifying the PCPs' ambivalence about PSA screening is crucial as patients depend on PCPs' guidance to weigh potential benefits and risks of PSA screening (Howard, Salkeld, Patel, Mann, & Pignone, 2015; Hutchinson et al., 2016; Pucheril et al., 2015). An adapted clinical tool on PSA testing based on current guidelines and evidence-based urological practices in conjunction with the Delphi panel helped clarify the primary care providers' ambivalence on PSA screening.

Figure 1. Modified and updated PSA testing tool.

METHODS

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to modify, develop and evaluate an evidence-based tool on PSA testing to improve appropriate urology referrals for prostate examinations by the primary care providers. The methods section has eight categories: 1) ethical consideration, 2) provider demographics and setting, 3) preliminary work, 4) procedures, 5) measure of outcomes, 6) data collection and analysis, 7) evaluation and instrument, and 8) sustainability. The project proposal was reviewed and approved by the project chair, project committee, and the California State University (CSU) DNP Consortium. The development of the clinical tool on PSA testing will proceed to the pilot testing phase with the primary care providers after graduation due to the time constraint of the DNP program.

Ethical Consideration

To establish the extent of the clinical issue, the EMR was reviewed at the Clinic to quantify the scope of inappropriate urology referrals for prostate examinations. To develop the modified PSA testing tool, no patient contact was planned; nor were any personal health information reviewed. Therefore, a Determination of Not Research Letter was received from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) at California State University, Long Beach (CSULB) on June 12, 2018 (Appendix D).

Provider Demographics and Setting

The Los Angeles area Clinic includes three urologists and one nurse practitioner who manage approximately 250 patients per week. The support staff consist of three front office personnel, one surgical scheduler, and three back office medical assistants. This practice serves a mostly geriatric Armenian and Hispanic population. The patients

are routinely scheduled for examinations, procedures, and surgeries, such as robotic prostatectomy. The patient population presents to the Clinic with mostly complex co-morbidities, which reinforce the need for a standardized clinical tool to better assess and manage their risks of harm from PSA screening. The clinical tool is being developed for primary care providers to help improve appropriate urology referrals for prostate examinations.

Preliminary Work

On December 2017, the Clinic's eClinicalWorks EMR system was accessed to obtain DRE and PSA testing information on the new male patients presenting to the Clinic for prostate exam from November 2016 to November 2017. Exclusion criteria consisted of other urological co-morbidities (e.g., adrenal mass). One hundred forty-eight patients were identified, 85 patients were excluded based on exclusion criteria, and 63 patients remained. Of these patients, 25 (40%) had normal prostate examinations where they did not need the urology referrals. Another four patients (6%) presented with advanced prostate cancer, who should have been referred much earlier. Finally, 34 patients (54%) were appropriately referred with abnormal PSA values and/or DREs.

Procedures

As demonstrated in the Clinic's data abstraction activity, the primary care providers' inconsistent urology referrals for prostate examinations were creating barriers for patients to obtain prompt urological services. To encourage consistently appropriate urology referrals, an evidence-based clinical tool was developed that incorporated user-centered design. The logic model was used to monitor and adjust the workflow. A Delphi panel of multidisciplinary physicians were assembled, consisting of four

clinicians specializing in internal medicine, radiation oncology, surgical pathology, and urology from the Los Angeles area to guide tool development. The recruitment of the panelists was from local physicians, who were blinded to each other's identify and responses. Two rounds of feedback were conducted using a modified Delphi method and quantitative analyses to develop consistent quality standards. The panelists graded, rated, and ranked key aspects of the tool to identify consensus definition on user-centered, evidence-based clinical tool on PSA testing.

Measures of Outcomes

The modified Delphi method used two rounds of structured feedback for consensus, which provided validity for the guideline. The structured feedback and rounds of edits helped strategize consensus definitions for the development of the final clinical tool for pilot testing.

In round one, the four Delphi panel members were asked to participate in an online questionnaire to explore necessary changes to existing clinical tools, definitions, and criteria based on their specialty in relation to the current guidelines (Appendix A; Appendix B; Appendix E). In round two, the Delphi panel was asked to establish consensus definitions and criteria through selecting and ranking feedback. Round three was not necessary as majority of the consensus was reached by round two. The Delphi panelists were able to communicate in person, by phone/fax, or via email.

Data Collection and Analysis

Electronic documentations, notes, and recordings for each round were collected and archived. They were also available to the Delphi panel for further comment and revision.

Evaluation and Instrument

In round one, the Delphi panel was asked to review the components of the existing clinical tool by completing the online survey and suggest changes to definitions and criteria based on their specialty. In round two, the panel was asked to establish consensus definitions and criteria by ranking the definitions and criteria based on round one results. Round three was reserved to identify concepts if consensus could not be achieved and finalize their recommendations. Excel, Qualtrics, and SPSS platforms were used to analyze the data. As presented on the Project Timeline, based on the two rounds of consensus results, an algorithmic clinical tool was developed (Appendix C, Table A; Appendix G).

Sustainability

After the completion of the DNP program, a pilot study with the primary care providers will be conducted to further assess user satisfaction, and the finalized product will be distributed to local primary care providers to evaluate changes in referral patterns for prostate examinations.

RESULTS

Delphi Panel's Demographics

The multidisciplinary Delphi panel consisted of four Los Angeles area physicians specializing in internal medicine, radiation oncology, surgical pathology, and urology. The panelists were recruited in 2018 through local contact in the Los Angeles area to guide PSA testing tool development. The demographics table (Table 2) reports Delphi panelists' specialty area, years in practice, race/ethnicity, gender, and age.

Table 2

Demographics of the Delphi Panelists

ID	Specialty	Years in Practice	Race/Ethnicity	Gender	Age
1	Internal Medicine	19	Indian	F	41-50
2	Radiation Oncology	15	Not Identified	F	41-50
3	Surgical Pathology	18	White	F	61-70
4	Urology	17	Asian	M	51-60

The Delphi panel convened for two rounds of online questionnaire feedback on October 2, 2018 and October 16, 2018. Third round of feedback was not initiated as majority of the consensus feedback was reached by round two.

Round One

The Delphi panel was requested to provide feedback for three in depth questions regarding PSA testing (Appendix E; Table 3).

Table 3

The Delphi Panel's Round One Questionnaire

Questions

What population characteristics should be included for Prostate Specific-Antigen (PSA) screening? Please mark with "X" for all that apply.

Age (please circle or highlight range if selected): 40-49, 50-59, 60-69, 70-79, 80-89

Race

First Degree Family History

Digital Rectal Exam (DRE)

Prior PSA

Life expectancy greater than 10 years (If so, do you currently use a tool to calculate life expectancy greater than 10 years? (Please circle or highlight "Yes" or "No." Yes/No)

Based on the current PSA screening guidelines below, which of the following guidelines should PSA screening criteria follow? Please rank (1 being the most recommended and 6 being the least recommended)

AAFP

ACS

ACP

ASCO

AUA

USPSTF

As AUA suggests, should PSA value interpretation include age-adjusted PSA, density, velocity, and free/total ratio at the primary care level which are consistent with urological practices today? Please mark with an "X."

Yes

No

For question one, the Delphi panel was instructed to first evaluate given population characteristics that should be included for PSA screening (Figure 2). The Delphi panel all indicated that race, first degree Family history, DRE, and prior PSA are vital population characteristics that should be included in PSA screening. Three out of four (only exception was the surgical pathologist) Delphi panelists selected age and life expectancy greater than 10 years as essential indicators for PSA screening.

Figure 2. Results from round one question one.

For question two, the Delphi panel was then instructed to rank six leading PSA screening guidelines (figure 3). The guidelines to follow were ranked accordingly, 1) AUA (highest) = three out of four physicians, 2) ASCO = two out of four physicians, 3) ACS = two out of four physicians, 4) AAFP, ACP, ASCO, USPSTF each = one out of four physicians, 5) ACP = two out of four physicians, and 6) USPSTF (lowest) = two out of four physicians.

Figure 3. Results from round one question two.

The accompanying frequency results (Table 4) for ranking of guidelines to follow are numerically displayed for clarification.

Table 4

Frequency Results from Round One Question Two

#	Rank	1	2	3	4	5	6	Total
1.	AAFP	0% 0	25% 1	0% 0	25% 1	25% 1	25% 1	4
2.	ACP	25% 1	0% 0	0% 0	25% 1	50% 2	0% 0	4
3.	ACS	0% 0	25% 1	50% 2	0% 0	0% 0	25% 1	4
4.	ASCO	0% 0	50% 2	25% 1	25% 1	0% 0	0% 0	4
5.	AUA	75% 3	0% 0	0% 0	0% 0	25% 1	0% 0	4
6.	USPSTF	0% 0	0% 0	25% 1	25% 1	0% 0	50% 2	4

For question three, the Delphi panel was instructed to report whether PSA value interpretation should stay consistent with current urological practices today (Figure 4).

The Delphi panel all agreed “Yes.”

Figure 4. Results from round one question three.

Round Two

The Delphi panel was requested to provide feedback for three in depth questions regarding PSA testing (Appendix F; Table 5).

Table 5

The Delphi Panel's Round Two Questionnaire

Questions

Please specify population characteristic to be included for Prostate Specific-Antigen (PSA) screening?
Please mark with "X" for all that apply.

Age Range for Screening

- 40-49
 50-59
 60-69
 70-79
 80-89

For life expectancy greater than 10 years for screening, do you currently use a tool to calculate life expectancy?

- Yes
 No

Based on the questionnaire feedback, the top three PSA screening guidelines are listed below. Please rank (1 being the most recommended and 3 being the least recommended with no repeat numbers).

- ACS
 ASCO
 AUA
-

For question one, the Delphi panel was instructed to specify age range for PSA screening to reach consensus (Figure 5). The Delphi panel all agreed on the 50-59 age group as a population characteristic to be included for PSA screening, followed by two of four physician agreement for 40-49, 60-69, and 70-79 age groups. There was zero selection for PSA screening for 80-89 age group.

Figure 5. Results from round two question one.

For question two, the Delphi panel was questioned whether they currently use a tool for calculating life expectancy (Figure 6). Only the urologist from the Delphi panel selected “Yes.”

Figure 6. Results from round two question two.

For question three based on round one feedback, the Delphi panel was instructed to rank the top three PSA screening guidelines for consensus (Figure 7). The panelists rated AUA (first), ACS (second), and ASCO (third).

Figure 7. Results from round two question three.

After evaluating Excel, Qualtrics, and SPSS statistical analyses of correlation coefficient between the six major PSA screening guidelines, the *p* value remained statistically insignificant (*p* = .986) due to the panel’s small group size and limited questions.

DISCUSSION

Using the modified Delphi method to achieve consensus definitions among the relevant multidisciplinary specialists, the PSA testing tool was modified and updated to improve appropriate urology referrals for prostate examinations (Appendix G).

During the Delphi panel's feedback phase, successful collaboration among the four panelists was essential in achieving the deadlines and goals of the project. Clear and prompt communication was needed to answer any questions and ensure proper feedback from clinically active physicians for two rounds of questionnaire.

In round one, the surgical pathologist was the only outlier in determining that age and life expectancy should not be included for PSA screening, which may be due to her older age range at 61-70 in comparison to other members who were mostly in the 41-60 age range group. This finding is similar to the previous research cited where primary care providers' years in practice; thus, age was a significant factor in determining whether to recommend USPSTF's PSA screening guidelines (Donnelly et al., 2017; Hall et al, 2017).

Although the panelists were blinded to each other's identify and responses, in round two, the panelists demonstrated subtle differences from the round one results. For example, in determining the best guidelines for PSA screening, with addition of time and narrowing of choices down to top three choices for ranking, the Delphi panel's consensus slightly deferred from round one. In addition, despite three out of four of the multidisciplinary panelists agreeing on the importance of including life expectancy greater than 10 years as part of the PSA screening characteristics, the urologist in the panel was the only provider who used a tool to calculate life expectancy.

A multidisciplinary Delphi panel's feedback was essential in developing a measurable consensus definition to help update currently significant PSA screening tool. Future studies with a larger group of multidisciplinary panelists and more in-depth questions may be helpful to ensure generalizability.

As outlined by the American Association of Colleges of Nursing (2006) in the Essentials for DNP prepared clinicians, the modified and updated tool on PSA testing using the modified Delphi method clearly demonstrates appropriate application of evidence-based knowledge to clinical practice. The DNP prepared clinicians must provide leadership skills that illustrate the ability to transform research knowledge into clinically applicable quality improvement projects. The integration and utilization of multidisciplinary teams are especially important to promote interest and compliance among key stakeholders.

This DNP project demonstrates leadership through the integration of the multidisciplinary Delphi panel to help bridge current evidence-based research with real-time clinical practice. As a result, a modified and updated PSA testing tool was developed with user-centered design methods to address identified clinical needs within the context of continuously evolving and increasingly global health care system.

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APPENDIX A

UNIVERSITY OF TEXAS, PROSTATE CANCER SCREENING TOOL

Prostate Cancer Screening

This practice algorithm has been specifically developed for MD Anderson using a multidisciplinary approach and taking into consideration circumstances particular to MD Anderson, including the following: MD Anderson's specific patient population; MD Anderson's services and structure; and MD Anderson's clinical information. Moreover, this algorithm is not intended to replace the independent medical or professional judgment of physicians or other health care providers.

PSA = prostate specific antigen
 DRE = digital rectal exam
 See Footnotes on Page 3

APPENDIX B

NATIONAL COMPREHENSIVE CANCER NETWORK,
PROSTATE CANCER SCREENING TOOL

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National
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DiscussionINDICATIONS FOR BIOPSY⁹

MANAGEMENT

- Repeat PSA
- DRE, if not performed during initial risk assessment
- Workup for benign disease

- Consider percent free PSA, 4Kscore, or PHI^h
- Consider multiparametric MRI^j

TRUS-guided biopsy^l

or

Follow up in 6–12 mo with PSA/DRE^{h,k}See Management
of Biopsy Results
(PROSD-4)TRUS-GUIDED BIOPSY
Initial and Repeat
Extended-pattern biopsy (12 cores)

- Number of cores:
 - ▶ Sextant (6),
 - ▶ Lateral peripheral zone (6), and
 - ▶ Lesion-directed at palpable nodule or suspicious image
- Anteriorly directed biopsy is not supported in routine biopsy. However, the addition of a transition zone biopsy to an extended biopsy protocol may be considered in a repeat biopsy if PSA is persistently elevated.
- Multiparametric MRI (MP MRI) followed by lesion targeting may maximize the detection of higher risk disease and limit the detection of lower risk disease.^j
- Local anesthesia can decrease pain/discomfort associated with prostate biopsy and should be offered to all patients.

⁹The level of PSA correlates with the risk of prostate cancer. The Prostate Cancer Prevention Trial (PCPT) demonstrated that 15% of men with a PSA level of ≤ 4.0 ng/mL and a normal DRE had prostate cancer diagnosed on end-of-study biopsies. Approximately 30% to 35% of men with serum PSA between 4 to 10 ng/mL will be found to have cancer. Total PSA levels >10 ng/mL confer a greater than 87% likelihood of prostate cancer.

^hBiomarkers that improve the specificity of detection are not, as yet, recommended as first-line screening tests. However, there may be some patients who meet PSA standards for consideration of prostate biopsy, but for whom the patient and/or the physician wish to further define the probability of high-grade cancer. A percent free PSA $<10\%$, PHI >35 or 4Kscore (which provides an estimate of the probability of high-grade prostate cancer) are potentially informative in patients who have never undergone biopsy or after a negative biopsy; a PCA3 score >35 is potentially informative after a negative biopsy. The predictive value of the serum biomarkers discussed above has not been correlated with that of MRI. Therefore it is not known how such tests could be applied in optimal combination.

^kFor patients with abnormal DRE, biopsy or additional testing should be considered based on concern for cancer.

^lEmerging data suggest that, in men undergoing initial biopsy, targeting using MRI/ultrasound fusion may significantly increase the detection of clinically significant, higher-risk (Gleason grade $\geq 4+3=7$) disease while lowering the detection of lower-risk (Gleason sum 6 or lower-volume Gleason grade 3+4=7) disease. Siddiqui M, Rais-Bahrami S, Turkbey B, et al. Comparison of MRI/ultrasound Fusion-Guided Biopsy With Ultrasound-Guided Biopsy for the Diagnosis of Prostate Cancer. JAMA 2015;313:390-7. Ahmed H, Bosaily A, Brown L, et al. Diagnostic accuracy of multi-parametric MRI and TRUS biopsy in prostate cancer (PROMIS): a paired validating confirmatory study. Lancet 2017;389:815-822.

^jPatients with a persistent and significant increase in PSA should be encouraged to undergo TRUS-guided biopsy.

Note: All recommendations are category 2A unless otherwise indicated.
Clinical Trials: NCCN believes that the best management of any patient with cancer is in a clinical trial. Participation in clinical trials is especially encouraged.

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PROSD-3

APPENDIX C

PROJECT TIMELINE

Table A

Project Timeline

January 2018	February 2018	March 2018	April 2018	May 2018	June 2018
	2/11 Problem statement	3/4 Conceptual framework	4/8 Review of literature & Table of evidence	5/18 Project proposal	Institutional Review Board
			4/22 Methods		
July 2018	August 2018	September 2018	October 2018	November 2018	December 2018
	Recruit Delphi panelists	Recruit Delphi panelists	10/2 Round One Delphi panel's feedback	Project data analyses	Final clinical tool and project proposal
			10/16 Round Two Delphi panel's feedback		
January 2019	February 2019	March 2019	April 2019	May 2019	
First draft manuscript	2/14 Final manuscript	3/27 Present poster	4/27 Final defense	5/23 Graduation	

APPENDIX D**IRB'S DETERMINATION OF NOT RESEARCH LETTER****CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH****OFFICE OF RESEARCH & SPONSORED PROGRAMS**

DATE: June 12, 2018

TO: Jacklyn Jump
FROM: CSULB IRB

PROJECT TITLE: [1251741-1] Improving Urology Referrals for Prostate Examinations
REFERENCE #: 18-429
SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project

ACTION: DETERMINATION OF NOT RESEARCH
DECISION DATE: June 12, 2018

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board has determined this project does not meet the definition of human subject research under the purview of the IRB according to federal regulations at 45 CFR 46.101, U.S. Department of Health and Human Services (HHS). This project involves the use of aggregate secondary data to develop an evidence-based tool to improve urology referrals for prostate exams then incorporating the Delphi method and pilot project to evaluate the tool. All aforementioned project activities do not satisfy the definition of research with human subjects because the project does not contribute to generalizable knowledge and does not involve the use of human subjects' data.

We will retain a copy of this correspondence within our records.

If you have any questions, please contact the CSULB IRB at (562) 985-8147 or IRB@csulb.edu. Please include your project title and reference number in all correspondence with this committee.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board's records.

APPENDIX F

ROUND TWO QUESTIONNAIRE FEEDBACK

Please specify population characteristic to be included for Prostate Specific-Antigen (PSA) screening? Pleaes mark with "X" for all that apply.					
Age Range for Screening					
ID	40-49	50-59	60-69	70-79	80-89
1	x	x			
2		x	x	x	
3		x			
4	x	x	x	x	
For life expectancy greater than 10 years for screening, do you currently use a tool to calculate life expectancy?					
ID	Yes	No			
1		x			
2		x			
3		x			
4	x				
Based on the questionnaire feedback, the top three PSA screening guidelines are listed below. Please rank (1 being the most recommended and 3 being the least recommended with no repeat numbers).					
ID	ACS	ASCO	AUA		
1	2	3	1		
2	3	2	1		
3	2	3	1		
4	2	3	1		

APPENDIX G

MODIFIED AND UPDATED PSA TESTING TOOL

APPENDIX H
TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Table H1

PSA Screening Practices

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/ Limitations
To determine whether there is ↓ in PCA mortality from PSA screening and DRE (Andriole et al., 2012)	Experimental, randomized study	Randomized 76, 685	Comparison of PCA mortality rates between IG and CG	At 13 yrs follow-up in 2009, 4250 pts had PCA in the IG and 3815 pts in the CG	No mortality benefit from generalized PCA screening
	IV: PCA screening DV: PCA mortality	IG: N = 38,340 CG: N = 38,345 Multicenter, multiple states IC: men 55 – 74 yrs with no personal hx of PCA EC: current ca tx, previous sx removal of the entire prostate, participation in another ca	Comparison of PCA incidence rates between IG and CG	Mortality rates in the IG versus CG were 3.7 and 3.4 deaths per 10,000 person-years, no statistically significant difference (RR = 1.09, 95% CI = 0.87 to 1.36)	Limitation: Contamination from opportunistic PSA screening as 45% randomly assigned pts had at least one PSA test in the last 3 yrs with approximately 52% PSA screening in the CG

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/Limitations
		screening, use of Finasteride within 6 months			
To evaluate whether pt characteristics or prostate needle biopsy results changed after 2012 USPSTF recommendation against PSA screening (Banerji et al., 2016)	Retrospective cohort study Predictor: PSA screening guidelines Outcome: PNB results, clinical & demographic pt characteristics	Pre-USPSTF: N = 1,416 Pre-USPSTF draft N = 448 (sub sample of the pre-USPSTF) Post-USPSTF: N = 310 Multicenter registry, Seattle, Washington IC: all first PNB 2004 – 2014, historical control group without PNB EC: pts with known PCA, no PSA prior to biopsy, biopsy between 10/08/2011 and 05/24/2012 during	Researcher generated chart abstraction tool	1948 pts had PNB between 2004-2014 Post-USPSTF group had ↑ PSA ($p < .001$), ↑ clinical stage diagnosis (2b, $p = .003$, 2c-3a, $p = .027$) compared to pre-USPSTF group D’Amico high risk prostate cancer with adjusted RR for high risk prostate cancer of 1.25 (95% CI 1.02 - 1.52, $p = .036$), compared to pre-USPSTF group 30 months pre-USPSTF draft	Significant ↑ in diagnosis of ↑ risk disease following PNB after USPSTF recommendation ↓ in PNB decreased detection of potentially curable intermediate risk disease Future efforts on informed decision about PSA screening to improve mortality rate Limitations: historical PSA information, one multispecialty center

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/Limitations
		USPSTF draft, and less than 10 core biopsies		group demonstrated similar results Post-USPSTF group demonstrated 31% ↓ in biopsies performed, mostly in intermediate risk tumors	
To examine relative risks of PCA incidence, metastasis, and mortality related to PSA screening levels at age 60 years (Carlsson et al., 2014)	Population based retrospective cohort study Predictor: PSA screening levels Outcome: Effects on prostate cancer incidence, metastasis, and mortality	N = 1,756, PSA screened men since 1995. N = 1,162, PSA unscreened men from stored blood samples from 1981 IC: All first PSA screening from 1995 - 1996 EC: Ages 57.5 - 62.5 at baseline Multicenter, Sweden	Researcher generated statistical analysis to compare incidence rate ratios	PSA screening level distribution similar between two groups. From pts with baseline PSA, 71.7% had PSA value < 2 ng/mL (95% CI). Pts aged 60 with PSA level < 2 ng/mL had ↑ incidence of 767 cases per 10,000 without ↓ in PCA mortality	Men with PSA level < 1 ng/mL at age 60 should not screen further, men with PSA level ≥ 2 mg/mL at age 60 should screen to avoid preventable PCA mortality Future focus should be on men at ↑ risk with PSA screening level ≥ 2 ng/mL for harm/benefit study of PSA screening Limitations: 15 yrs follow-up may be too

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/ Limitations
				Pts with PSA levels ≥ 2 ng/mL exhibited significant \downarrow in PCA mortality with only 23 pts needing to be screened, and 6 diagnosed to avoid 1 PCA death by 15 years	short given long clinical progression of PCA, moderate sample size, and homogenous population
To quantify outcome of pts diagnosed and treated for PCA in single institution	Population based retrospective cohort study Predictor: diagnosis and treatment of PCA	Men at age 60 diagnosed with PCA between 1960 to 2009. Cancer registry and EMR N = 6,181	Researcher generated statistical analysis to measure clinical PCA variables on treatment outcome	PSA test did not seem to change tx outcome. Age, grade, and stage were largest predictors of PCA outcome	MC's PCA pts followed national trend of \downarrow age of dx and similar tx outcome since PSA screening
(Cross et al., 2011)	Outcome: quantify effects on PCA treatment outcome	Marshfield Clinic (MC) in Wisconsin IC: adult males with PCA dx EC: PCA from 1990 to 2008		PSA levels ≤ 2 ng/mL, \uparrow in incidence of 767 cases per 10,000 without a \downarrow in PCA mortality PSA levels ≥ 2 ng/mL, only 23 men needed to be	Clinical focus should be on age, grade, and stage to predict PCA outcome Limitations: Single institution with 97% Caucasian population does not reflect high risk African American group

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/Limitations
				screened and six diagnosed to avoid one PCA mortality by 15 yrs	
To evaluate recommendations for PSA screening in national survey of radiation oncologists and urologists post-USPSTF recommendation against PSA screening (Kim et al., 2014)	Non-experimental, descriptive	Phase 1, random sample of 50 radiation oncologists and 50 urologists sent pilot survey questionnaire, which was revised Phase 2, random sample 1,366 radiation oncologists and urologists targeted (American Association Physician Masterfile) IC/EC: physicians who completed residency training, < 65 years, involved in patient	Survey sent in 4 waves to assess whether PSA screening was recommended for men with average risk in following age categories: 40 - 49, 50 - 59, 60 - 69, 70 - 74, 75 - 79, and ≥ 80 years	Similar response rates: 52% radiation oncologists & urologists ($p = .92$). 51.1% recommended PSA screening for men aged 40 - 49 years, 96.1% for 50 - 59 years, 97.3% for 60 -69, 87.7% for 70 - 74 years, 43.9% and 12.8% for 75 – 79/ ≥80 years. Multivariable analysis demonstrated ↑ urologists recommending PSA screening for men aged 40 - 49 (OR 3.09,	Radiation oncologists and urologists recommended PSA screening for men aged 50 - 69 years with recommendation inconsistencies for younger age 40 - 49 years and older age ≥ 70 yrs Limitations: survey timing after recent release of USPSTF preliminary recommendation against PCA screening may have influenced feedback, low response rate may have biased findings, and surveys targeted specialists rather than primary care providers

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/Limitations
		care, practicing in US		$p = .001$)/50 - 59 years (OR 3.81, $p = .01$), but ↓men aged 75 - 79 (OR 0.66, $p = .01$) /≥80 years (OR 0.45, $p = 0.002$), compared to radiation oncologists	who mostly confront PCA screening issues
To investigate PSA population screening in a systematic review (Lee et al., 2013)	Systematic review and meta-analysis of prior systematic reviews IV: population-based PSA screening DV: PCA mortality and detection rate	Most relevant reviews and additional literature search Searched Ovid, Medline, Embase, Cochrane library, and the major Korean databases Two reviewers independently used AMSTAR to assess quality of systematic reviews IC/EC: asymptomatic	Cochrane group's risk of bias tool to assess quality of randomized controlled trials	Detection of stage 1 PCA did not improve with high heterogeneity; however, PCA mortality and dx at stages 3-4 demonstrated moderate level of evidence	PSA screening alone did not ↑ stage 1 PCA detection nor mortality, but did demonstrate moderate level of evidence for stages 3-4 PCA PSA screening demonstrates promise of detecting more advanced PCA when prompt intervention may be valuable to decrease mortality Limitations: Screening only asymptomatic pts rather than including

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/Limitations
		males >40 yrs with PSA population screening with no restriction on region or race			high-risk groups, Europe and US only
To provide updated results of PCA mortality following 2010 ERSPC that found PSA screening significantly ↓ PCA mortality (Shröder et al., 2014)	Experimental, randomized study using centralized database 9, 11 and 13 years of follow-up to initial clinical trial of 2010 IV: PSA screening DV: reduction in PCA mortality	Pts from multicenter, 8 European countries: Netherlands, Belgium, Sweden, Finland, Italy, Spain, Switzerland, France. N = 72,891 IG, N = 89,352 CG, between 55 - 69 years, randomly assigned by computer IC: men aged 50 - 74 at randomization EC: men with death date before randomization	Screening and Indication for biopsy: PSA in serum, cutoff of > 3.0 ng/mL and 3.0 - 3.9 ng/mL in Finland and Italy Sextant biopsies for screen-positive men	At 13 years 7,408 IG and 6,107 CG had PCA. Rate ratio of PCA between IG and CG 1.91 (1.64 including France) after 9 years, 1.66 after 11 years, 1.57 after 13 years. Rate ratio of PCA mortality 0.85 after 9 years, 0.78 after 11 years, 0.79 at 13 years. Lack of difference in PCA mortality between 11 and 13 years may be due to France being included for analysis of incidence, but not mortality. At 13	Confirmed 2010 study findings. ↓ prostate cancer mortality in IG compared to CG related to PSA screening based on 13 years of follow-up Future efforts on ↓ harm due to overdiagnosis/overtreatment, and informed decision between clinicians and patients about PSA screening to ↑ mortality rate Limitations: France only included for short follow-up due to poor compliance with biopsy, 13 years of follow-up not long

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/ Limitations
				years, PCA mortality 0.43/1,000 IG, 0.54/1,000 CG persons-years (95% CI, $p = .001$)	enough as early prostate cancer growth between 15-25 years, 23-40% contamination in CG

Table H2

Practice Patterns and Attitudes of Primary Care Providers

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/Limitations
To assess PCPs' PSA screening trends after 2012 USPSTF recommendation against PSA screening in all men (Cohn et al., 2014)	Population based retrospective cohort study Predictor: 2012 USPSTF recommendation Outcome: ↓ PCPs' PSA screening trends after 2012	Electronic data warehouse to identify men 40-79 years evaluated by PCPs during June-November 2011 before USPSTF recommendation, June-November 2012 after USPSTF recommendation, resulted in 112,221 pts EC: history of PCA or urology visit	Pt age calculated by decades of life, PSA history by <1.0, 1.0-2.49, 2.5-4.0, > 4.0 ng/ml	↓ in screening frequency post USPSTF recommendation group (8.6% pre vs. 7.6% post, $p = .0001$, OR = 0.89, 95% confidence interval 0.83 – 0.95). 40-49 years group (5.6% pre vs. 4.6% post, $p = .0004$). 70-79 years group (7.9% pre vs. 6.2% post, $p = .01$). ↓ PSA screening with previous PSA <1.0 ng/ml ($p < .0001$) and PSA 1.0-2.49 ng/ml ($p = .0074$)	Post 2012 USPSTF recommendation found continuing ↓ in PCPs' PSA screening trends. Significant downward trend in youngest, oldest, pts with PSA < 2.5 ng/ml suggest selective screening practices African American men with high risk for PCA may be under-screened and harmed by recommendation against PSA screening Limitations: Excluding large pool of potential urologist pts, weakness of observational study influencing change, short 6-month data

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/ Limitations
To assess PCA screening practices of Vermont PCPs (Donnelly et al., 2017)	Non-experimental, descriptive	123 of 453 completed surveys. Electronic survey emailed to all practicing PCPs through Vermont Medical Society Registry of Vermont Providers IC/EC: all currently practicing PCP's in Vermont	Survey to assess use of DRE and PSA for PCA screening among PCPs	Physicians in practice ≥ 10 yrs significantly more likely to use PSA and DRE screening tools, consistent with 2001 study Physicians who continued to use PSA screening were less likely to stop screening after 80 yrs (51% in 2014 vs. 74% in 2001, $p < 0.001$) and initiated fewer DRE screening before age 50 in 2014 compared with 2001 96.1% who changed PCA screening behavior	comparison, limited patient characteristics PCA screening practices among Vermont PCPs vary by yrs in practice. Screening men > 80 yrs may not detect clinically significant disease Focus should be on high risk men who are African-American, with strong family history, BRCA mutation, or Lynch Syndrome Limitations: sample limited to Vermont with low response rate

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/Limitations
To evaluate whether PSA screening men >70 years affect prostate cancer incidence in the U.S. (Gulati et al., 2014)	Retrospective and prospective cohort study Predictor: PSA screening Outcome: ↓ PCA mortality men >70 years	FHCRC and UMICH models used to predict mortality rates during 2013-2025 for men >70 years based on PSA screening/ discontinued PSA screening	Predict incidence and mortality rates 2013 - 2025 with PSA screening and without PSA screening for all men or men >70 yrs	cited USPSTF for their decision	
				Between 2013-2025, PSA screening between two models predicted mortality rates for men >70 years correlated overdiagnosis of 710,000-1,120,000 men, but avoided 36,000-57,000 preventable PCA deaths	Discontinuing PSA screening for all men may encourage preventable PCA related deaths, especially men <70 years where PSA screening halved preventable PCA related deaths, significantly ↓ overdiagnoses compared to all men
				Discontinued PSA screening resulted in 0% overdiagnoses, but failed to prevent 100% preventable PCA deaths	Clinical implication is despite overdiagnosis, continue PSA screening to avoid significant number of preventable PCA deaths
				Continued PSA screening for men <70 years eliminated 64% to 66%	Limitations: health status, life expectancy, coarse grade categories, predictive

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/Limitations
				overdiagnoses, but failed to prevent 36% to 39% preventable PCA deaths	estimates to future year to 2025
To examine 2016 data on PCPs' PSA screening behaviors and beliefs (Hall et al., 2017)	Non-experimental, descriptive	DocStyles web-based survey of US PCPs. 1,256 completed surveys IC: current and active providers, who worked at least three yrs in the US EC: Restricted to family and internal medicine	Nine clinical factors involved in the decision to use PSA screening among asymptomatic men	61% of pts recommended PSA screening based on individual risk factors, rather than routinely for all men More yrs of practice significantly associated with recommending PSA screening	Reduction in routine PSA screening from estimate 80% in 2008 to about quarter of PCPs sampled post-USPSTF recommendation Encourage shared decision about PSA screening for men 55-69 yrs Limitations: pts may not accurately represent PCPs in the US due to subjective, self-reported data
To assess men's preferences for PSA screening, benefits and harms	Non-experimental, descriptive Discrete choice experiment (DCE) with a two-step pilot	662 Australian men with no family hx of PCA for web-based survey by an external organization	Influences on men's PSA testing decisions	Men's preferences were significantly influenced by potential mortality benefit, unnecessary	Differences in trade-offs acceptable to men of different ages

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/Limitations
(Howard et al., 2015)	study and final DCE design	IC/EC: men 40-69 yrs with no dx or tx of PCA		<p>biopsies, and potential urinary incontinence/bowel issues, age, prior PSA testing, and perceived risk of PCA</p> <p>65 - 233 of 10,000 men were willing to accept unnecessary biopsies, and 31 - 72 of 10,000 men were willing to accept incontinence/bowel problems to avoid one PCA mortality</p>	<p>Encourage shared decision making of risk/benefit</p> <p>Limitations: pts stated behavior may not represent actual behavior, and the online pts may not represent men in general community</p>
To analyze PSA ordering and referral practices yrs surrounding USPSTF recommendation against PSA screening	<p>Retrospective study</p> <p>IV: surrounding USPSTF recommendation</p> <p>DV: PSA ordering and referral practices</p>	<p>63,722 raw PSA orders with eventual 54,684 evaluable orders. Administrative database from single tertiary care institution. Pts subdivided by PSA</p>	Changes in trends of PSA ordering and referral behavior	<p>PCPs ordered 17,315 PSA tests and 858 urology referrals</p> <p>PSA values at time of referral increased significantly</p>	<p>PSA behaviors did not change significantly, but pts referred at progressively higher average PSA levels</p> <p>Establishing early PSA trend may be necessary to detect ↑</p>

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/Limitations
(Hutchinson et al., 2016)		level within set categories IC: male patients between 2010 to 2015 EC: No exclusions to PSA examinations based on age, race, family hx, or medical hx		No joinpoints in the analysis of total PSA orders, screening PSA tests, or examinations per 100 visits	PSA and ↓ progressively higher average PSA levels when referred to urologists where tx becomes more difficult Limitations: Lack of nonintervention group of providers, single-site study, and drop-off in PCA dx starting 2007 prior to 2012 USPSTF recommendation
To examine changes in PCA stages and PSA screening rates after 2008 and 2012 USPSTF recommendation (Jemal et al., 2015)	Retrospective study IV: 2008 and 2012 USPSTF recommendation DV: changes in PCA stages and PSA screening rates	Cancer registry data and National Interview Survey (NHIS) from 2005 to 2012 using 18 population-based registries 2005 (N = 4580), 2008 (N = 3475), 2010 (N = 4157), 2013 (N = 6172)	PCA incidence and incidence ratios comparing PCA stages and PSA screening rates 2005 - 2012	PCA incidence per 100,000 men ≥50 yrs was 534.9 in 2005, 540.8 in 2008, 505.0 in 2010, and 416.2 in 2012. Declines since 2008 were confined to local/regional-stage disease	PSA screening ↓ since 2008 and continued after 2012 USPSTF recommendation Longer study needed to determine impact on mortality Limitations: PSA screening ↓ before 2012 USPSTF recommendation,

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/Limitations
		IC/EC: men \geq 50 yrs without hx of PCA US Population		Incidence of men \geq 50 yrs reporting PSA screening in the past 12 months was 36.9% in 2005, 40.6% in 2008, 37.8% in 2010, and 30.8% in 2013	based on self-reported data with potential recall bias
To evaluate PCP's perspectives on recommendation against PSA screening (Pollack et al., 2012)	Non-experimental, descriptive	Recruited 125 pts from Johns Hopkins Community Physicians (JHCP) university-affiliated practice, Maryland IC/EC: In 2010, 40,000 men aged \geq 40 yrs who attended JHCP site were eligible for PCA screening, which produced 141 potential pts	Barriers to discontinuing PSA screening with clinicians' perspectives	59.3% considered both age and life expectancy into account, and 12.2% did not consider either Providers differed in age to stop screening with 66.4% having difficulty assessing life expectancy Barriers to discontinue PSA screening were patient expectation (74.4%) and time	Although age and life expectancy were supposed to factor in whether to PSA screen or not, PCPs face multiple barriers to end PSA screening Shared decision-making is crucial to address barriers Limitations: potential nonresponse bias, self-report, survey was conducted shortly after 2012 USPSTF recommendation

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/Limitations
				constraints (66.4%)	
To examine influence of physicians' PSA screening recommendation on patients' decision (Pucheril et al., 2015)	Non-experimental, descriptive	2012, data from Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System (BRFSS) IC/EC: Men ≥ 55 with no hx of PCA or prostate "problem" with PSA test within the preceding year	Calculate odds of screening	75% men informed of screening benefits 32% men informed of screening risks After being informed of benefits/risks, 56% men opted for PSA screening if provided recommended it compared to 21% without recommendation	Patients' decision for PSA screening was greatly influenced by PCPs' recommendation Shared decision-making along with PCPs' recognition of their bias are important Limitations: potential recall and nonresponse bias
To examine PCPs' perspective on using decision aids for PSA testing (Rim et al., 2018)	Non-experimental, descriptive	2016 DocStyles annual web-based survey of U.S. healthcare professionals Primary care physicians n = 1,003, Nurse	Beliefs and attitudes about using the PSA screening, factors for decision to recommend (or not), use of decision aid to	11% providers used decision aids. 54% did not use decision aid but were interested. 46% wanted a newer/improved decision aid	Opportunity exists for evaluating and improving existing decision aids for PCA screening Limitations: Although all major guidelines encourage

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/Limitations
		practitioners n = 253	assist decision-making	25% routinely offered PSA screening. 59% offered PSA screening based on risk factors. 16% did not offer PSA test 52% used shared-decision making. 41% providers decided on their own	shared decision-making for PSA testing, time limitation was a barrier for thorough discussions and exploration of existing tools Survey items did not differentiate between provider or patient decision aid Selection/social desirability bias and small sample size
To evaluate the effects of printed educational material on PCA screening (Stamatiou et al., 2008)	Experimental, randomized design IV: educational material on PCA screening by PSA and DRE DV: changes to PSA and DRE screening decisions	1,500 men attended researchers' institutions where pts with non-prostate-related conditions were randomly assigned to two study groups after pre-test interview with the physician	Knowledge measure	After 24 months, no statistically significant difference between two groups for DRE (4% IG, 5% CG) while for PSA screening, 31% CG versus 93% IG participated in PSA screening	PCA screening printed educational material changed pts' attitude towards PSA screening, but not DRE Since both PSA and DRE are critical components of complete prostate examination, clinicians' efforts

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/Limitations
		IG received educational material on PCA screening by their physicians after discussion, while CG only discussed about PCA screening		Educational level and residence were strong predictors of PCA knowledge ($p < 0.05$)	should target both tests especially in rural/isolated areas Limitations: high percentage of DRE refusal, no assessment of educational knowledge being barrier to PCA screening
		IC/EC: men 50 to 86 yrs with PCP appt at researchers' institutions from 2004 to 2006 for medical conditions except prostate-related conditions			
To identify patterns in PCPs' knowledge and attitudes towards PSA screening, and determine if demographics influence PSA screening preferences	Non-experimental, descriptive	82 physicians completed the surveys mailed to PCPs' at UCSF Medical Center, San Francisco General Hospital, and San Francisco Veteran's Administration Medical Center	Knowledge measure	98% identified African American race as a prostate cancer risk factor 42% DRE and PSA as acceptable PCA screening 59% underestimated	Pts less knowledgeable about PCA screening and overall PCA risks Most pts were not confident in their knowledge and did not screen men > 50

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Conclusions/Limitations
(Tasian et al., 2012)		IC/EC: faculty and resident physicians in internal or family medicine at three medical centers in San Francisco		chance of PCA in men with PSA level >4 ng/ml 19% PCPs were confident in PCA knowledge 86% screened fewer than 60% of male pts \geq 50 age (identified 2012 USPSTF recommendation/practice guidelines)	Shared decision-making along with PCPs' recognition of their bias are important Limitations: potential recall and nonresponse bias

Note. BPH = Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia, CA = cancer, CEBM = Oxford Centre for Evidence-Based Medicine, CG = Control Group, CI = Confidence Interval, DX = Diagnosis, DRE = Digital Rectal Exam, DV = Dependent Variable, EC = Exclusion Criteria, EMR = Electronic Medical Record, ERSPC = European Randomized Study of Screening for Prostate Cancer, FHCRC = Fred Hutchinson Cancer Research Center, HX = History, IC = Inclusion Criteria, IG = Intervention Group, IV = Independent Variable, OR = Odds Ratio, PCA = Prostate Cancer, PCP = Primary Care Providers, PNB = Prostate Needle Biopsy, PSA = Prostate-Specific Antigen, PCP = Primary Care Providers, Pt = Participant, RR = Relative Risk, SX = Surgery, TRUS = Transrectal Ultrasound Guided, TX = Treatment, UMICH = University of Michigan, US = United States, USPSTF = U.S. Preventative Services Task Force, YRS = Years